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Notes

1. <https://w3id.org/simulation/docs>
2. <https://spacy.io/>
3. We measure cosine similarities between vectors of symbols and symbolic meanings generated using the mentioned models.
4. Similarity = 1-graph edit distance

Inner- and Intra-genre Citation Patterns in Film

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“[A]ny text is the absorption and transformation of another” (Kristeva, 1986) and thus part of a dynamically evolving network of influences. This also applies to film. However, quantitative efforts dissected influence phenomena in film so far only at the individual level (Sreenivasan, 2013; Wasserman et al., 2014; Bioglio and Pensa, 2018). To instead assess inner- and intra-genre citation patterns and thereby challenge hitherto valid genre attributions, we propose the exploitation of three group-dependent network. To this end, genres are considered as fluid, perpetually rearranging concepts (Bordwell, 1989). We leverage user-contributed data from the Internet Movie Database (IMDb).¹ Four types of citations serve as proxies for influence: “edits,” “features,” “references,” and “spoofs”; whereby influence may be an expression of common narratives, settings, or techniques (Lakoff, 1987).

Methods

We regard film citation networks as directed acyclic graphs $G=(V,E)$ consisting of a set of $|V|=N$ films and $|$

$E| = M$ citations. The directionality of G depends on the order of time: a film x can only cite another film y if y was sufficiently distributed before x . For reasons of simplicity, we assume that G is observed at discrete and equidistant time points $t=1, \dots, T$ only, so that $G(t)=(V, E_t)$ indicates the state of G at time point t . Each state reflects the citations available up until t for films that were produced before t . Over the past decades, numerous metrics have been proposed to determine the influence of such multi-actor collectives in social networks (Silva et al., 2014; Rad and Benyoucef, 2011). We hereinafter focus on three metrics that are interpretable and adaptable, even to humanities-related contexts not directly concerned with citation structures.

Group In-degree and Group Out-degree Centrality

Films are generally considered influential if they are cited by other media; the higher the number of citations received, the greater their perceived importance (Garfield, 1955). In network theory, this is known as *in-degree centrality*. Due to the simplicity of the metric, it is easily extendable to support the analysis of group-dependent citation patterns. As derived from Everett and Borgatti (1999), the *group in-degree centrality* of films associated with genre h can be expressed as the ratio of incoming citations at t from films of other genres, i.e.,

$$\text{deg}_h^-(t) = \frac{\sum_{v \in V_h} \text{deg}_{G(t)}^-(v) - \sum_{v \in V_h} \text{deg}_{G_h(t)}^-(v)}{\sum_{v \in V_h} \text{deg}_{G(t)}^-(v)}$$

Accordingly, the *group out-degree centrality*

$$\text{deg}_h^+(t) = \frac{\sum_{v \in V_h} \text{deg}_{G(t)}^+(v) - \sum_{v \in V_h} \text{deg}_{G_h(t)}^+(v)}{\sum_{v \in V_h} \text{deg}_{G(t)}^+(v)}$$

denotes the ratio of outgoing citations at t to films of genres other than h . Both help to quantify the external and internal willingness of films to establish connections outside their genre, thereby enabling us to trace the genre’s historical “evolution” through genre mixing and hybridization.

Group Triangle Participation Ratio

Genres are constructed by a syntax of recurring elements that develop with time (Altman, 1984). The more limited

their syntax, the more likely it is that groups with self-referential structures emerge, composed of intra-genre citation triads. We conclude that a film u in such groups not only cites films v and w , but v also cites w . The *group triangle participation ratio*

$$\text{tpr}_h(t) = \frac{\left| \left\{ u \mid \left\{ (u, v), (u, w), (v, w) \in E_h^{(t)} \right\} \neq \emptyset \right\} \right|}{|V_h|}$$

thus is the ratio of citation triads at t of films associated with genre h (cf. Yang and Leskovec, 2012).

Data

To assess genre citation patterns, we retrieve 40,621 feature-length films from the IMDb with a run time of more than 39 minutes that were produced before 2020 and are assigned to at least one of 22 genres. Like Bioglio and Pensa (2018), we observe a high number of films labeled as “drama” or “comedy,” with this categorization supported by other labels in 77.938 % and 75.656 % of cases, respectively (Fig. 1A). The IMDb defines eight types of citations that can be entered by users in the “connections” section of the website. We confine ourselves to presumably intentional allusions: of the 126,343 citations, references account for 67.778 % and features for 23.071 %, while spoofs and edits occur much less frequently, at 6.599 % and 2.552 %, respectively. Due to the American-centric bias of the IMDb (Wasserman et al., 2014; Bioglio and Pensa, 2018), we concentrate on films from Europe and North America; English-language films dominate our corpus with 70.978 %. Given that English films are seen more frequently worldwide than non-English ones, the fraction of both incoming and outgoing citations is also disproportionate, possibly underestimating the effect of non-English films and genre influences, like the Italian *giallo*.

Fig. 1: (A) Number of films by genre, subdivided by total number of genres stored for films of that genre. (B) Group-dependent metrics over time: group in-degree centrality (blue), out-degree centrality (orange), and triangle participation ratio

(green); with Monte Carlo generated standard deviation bands in lighter colors.

Results

In-degree and out-degree approximately follow power-law distributions, indicating that although most films are cited only few times, a highly influential minority is referenced by dozens (Wasserman et al., 2015; Bioglio and Pensa, 2018). Films that have decisively contributed to the formation or shift of genre identities are particularly important, as they are widely cited not only within but outside their genre (Tab. I).

We determine aforeintroduced metrics for each genre h at time point t . To assess distribution uncertainties, a Monte Carlo simulation with 400 iterations is conducted. At each iteration, genres are randomly redistributed from the underlying empirical frequency distribution. The genre distribution over time remains fixed while the genre distribution at t changes, allowing us to evaluate the approximately true impact of genre-communities. Genres that are predominantly characterized by formulaic narratives or stereotypical figures exhibit large discrepancies between simulated and observed values. For instance, the *group triangle participation ratio* of sci-fi and horror films nearly doubles between 1970 and 2000 with negligible mean simulated ratios (Fig. 1B). This effect is due to few significant genre films that have disrupted conventionalized schemes, triggering new recycling patterns. Standardization through intra-genre repetition seems to be virtually integral to the horror film, e.g., as the lower-than-expected *group in-degree* and *out-degree centrality* confirm. Three citation phases can be verified: gothic horror (*Frankenstein*, 1931), superseded by psychological and occult topoi (*Rosemary's Baby*, 1968) that are increasingly accompanied by slasher films (*The Texas Chain Saw Massacre*, 1974).

Rank	Title	in-degree	ratio _{in-degree_h}
1	Star Wars: Episode IV (1977)	1190	40.168
2	The Wizard of Oz (1939)	989	35.490
3	Psycho (1960)	624	62.340
4	Jaws (1975)	546	48.718
5	The Godfather (1972)	518	52.703
6	Casablanca (1942)	507	47.732
7	Citizen Kane (1941)	472	51.907
8	Gone with the Wind (1939)	461	52.278
9	The Shining (1980)	455	61.319
10	2001: A Space Odyssey (1968)	443	48.307
11	King Kong (1933)	395	40.253
12	Frankenstein (1931)	395	66.582
13	Taxi Driver (1976)	391	52.941
14	The Terminator (1984)	391	44.501
15	Star Wars: Episode V (1980)	389	48.072
16	E.T. the Extra-Terrestrial (1982)	385	34.545
17	Apocalypse Now (1979)	372	35.215
18	The Exorcist (1973)	369	46.612
19	Raiders of the Lost Ark (1981)	351	45.299
20	Night of the Living Dead (1968)	345	57.681

Tab. 1:
Films by in-degree, with ratio of intra-genre citations in percent.

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Notes

1. <https://www.imdb.com/>, accessed 16 March 2022.

Annotating 3D Scholarly Editions

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Annotation has a rich history in the digital humanities: from the by and large manually created text-based annotation found in the Text Encoding Initiative (Cummings 2008) which modelled print-based textual syntax and structures while augmenting the text with commentary; to structured data enabling linked data sources on the WWW in which dynamic annotations are created (Sorbara 2020); from standards such as IIIF which was developed to annotate non-textual electronic files such as audio and video (International Image Interoperability Framework), to automatic image annotation which utilises computer vision to classify and categorise images or parts of images (Abgaz, et al 2021; Wang et al, 2021). The theories, methods, and practices of human-generated annotation have been developed over centuries with its apotheosis, one might argue, in the meticulously researched and richly annotated scholarly editions of the late twentieth century (Shillingsburg 1996). As academics we have been schooled to create and understand the train of scholarship embedded in print-based annotative environments. It is less clear, however, how we are to interpret machine-generated annotation, as well as how the interface and inon-

textual annotation play a role in knowledge production and dissemination that is multimodal, interactive, and multisensorial (Apollon, et al 2014; Drucker 2013). These new modalities and environments for annotation raise new issues, such as how to make clear provenance, intention, and context, for both users of these editions, as well as for the scholarly record.

One such new environment that raises such issues is 3D Scholarly Editions. This paper will delve deeper into one aspect of these editions: that of the affordances and challenges in annotating a 3D Scholarly Edition (3DSE) in the form of a virtual world. Previously we have argued that a 3DSE can be likened to a digital edition of an analogue text (such as a novel or a historical document) in which the 3D model is considered the text, with the annotation being part of the apparatus that surrounds it (Schreibman and Papadopoulos 2019; Papadopoulos and Schreibman 2019). However, the metaphor is not a perfect one in that the 3D object is in itself a representation, a domain specific model which simplifies the complexity of the environment being represented. Thus unlike a digital scholarly edition of an analogue text, the “author” of the model (the creator of the 3D representation) can occupy the same role as the “editor”, i.e., the person who annotates and contextualises the model. Even if the modeller and the annotator are different people, the goal of the 3DSE is not to remediate authorial intent (Tanselle 1976) or in this case the intent of the modeller. Rather, the modeller is, we argue, another kind of editor in the text’s (re)construction. To further complicate the actors involved in the 3DSE, given the possibility of more dynamic annotation (e.g., linked data and computer vision), the role of the “editor” can also be assumed by non-human actors.

Therefore, the burden of transparency in indicating agency, intent, and the decisions that the (re)construction is based on is even more complex than in traditional (Digital) Scholarly Editions. Here annotations can take many forms. They can be non-textual, for example, to indicate uncertainty or ambiguity in the (re)construction process when the model created is, for example, of an artefact that no longer exists, or exists in a deteriorated, changed, or incomplete form (such as the reconstruction of a house from antiquity based on its foundations and/or other evidence), or a reconstruction of a church at a particular moment in time when what exists today is an amalgamation of different building phases. In addition to text, annotations can include markup, tags, GIS markers, metadata or paradata that augment understanding, levels of certainty, interpretation, representation or alternative reconstructions, in formats including images, audio, video, 3D, pre-rendered animation, and simulations.

Annotations can also be active or passive. In a 3DSE, an active annotation is triggered by the user based on their interaction within the virtual environment (e.g.,